

Factors affecting Handloom Output in India: Results from a Panel Based Study across the States

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Abstract:

Background

The Indian handloom sector is vital for providing employment and contributing to the economy, particularly in agricultural regions. The Fourth All-India Handloom Census shows 31.44 lakh households engaged in handloom work, with most earning less than Rs. 5,000 monthly. The industry is diverse in terms of income, education, and other factors, with a focus on women's empowerment. Additional research is needed to understand the economic conditions of weaver households across India.

Methods

The panel data used in this study comes from census reports titled "The National Handloom Census of Weavers and Allied Workers." The dynamics are modeled using panel data regression.

Results

The findings highlight the important contribution that membership in cooperatives, SHGs, and businesses makes to total productivity. For instance, access to critical supplies, raw materials, and member buy-back schemes. To ensure that the handloom industry continues to expand, proactive governmental interventions are required to place unorganized homes under the auspices of these organizations.

Conclusion

The Indian economy benefits greatly from the handloom sector. The key factors influencing the productivity of the handloom sector are examined in the current study. Two main factors impacting production are the number of families weaving and their participation in cooperative groups. To improve efficiency, the report recommends changes to government policies that would move disorganized units into organized structures.

Keywords: Cooperative Memberships, Empowerment of Handloom, Handloom Productivity, Panel data Regression, Policy Interventions

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1. Introduction

The Indian handloom sector is an age-old industry that has played a crucial role in providing employment opportunities and contributing to the economy. The sector holds significant importance in terms of its magnitude and potential for generating jobs. Because of its close ties to other vital industries like agriculture, the handloom sector is very crucial to the agricultural economy. It generates a steady demand for agricultural production by using agricultural items as inputs. Handloom is therefore highly valued in an economy such as India, where the majority of people still rely on the agricultural sector for their livelihood.

The "Fourth All-India Handloom Census" states, there are 31.44 lakh households in India engaged in handloom work, representing 13% growth compared to the previous census. Four Indian states (Assam, West Bengal, Manipur, and Tamil Nadu) collectively represent 1.8 million weaver households, which accounts for the total number in the country. Most weaver households (66.3%) make less than Rs. 5,000 a month and only three states (Goa, Uttarakhand, and Maharashtra) have 60% or more of weaver households earning more than this amount per month. However, many of these households rely on extra sources of income. Only 17.5 percent of families rely exclusively on weaving and earn more than Rs 5,000 per month. This also implies that for a significant portion of households engaged in weaving are critically relying on the handloom sector for their means of subsistence.

Apart from the poor economic conditions faced by the average weaver households, the information from the survey clearly shows the diversity of weaving households across the states in terms of the level of income generated, education, the average number of days engaged in weaving, type of cloth produced, input material used, location of the household, and social and financial inclusion, etc. However, only very few studies tried to explore these complex economic and social dynamics well. In this background, this study tries to explore the presence of any systematic factors behind the existing economic conditions of the weaver households across the states in India.

The field of the study has great importance as it specifically focuses on promoting women's empowerment. According to the last census, the sector employs more than 2.3 million female weavers and related workers. The handloom sector primarily operates within households, relying on labor provided by the whole family. Hence, the active participation of a significant proportion of women in any role within this industry has resulted in direct financial benefits for them, so granting them economic autonomy and enhancing their sense of self-value both within their households and in society at large.

The structure of this document is as follows. A quick summary of research in the handloom industry is given in the next section. The section that follows will provide details on the data and methods. The results and discussion will come next, with the paper's conclusion coming last.

2. Literature Review

Research was conducted to determine and evaluate the influence of a few key variables on the improved living conditions of weavers in the state of Andhra Pradesh's Srikakulam district. Several key variables that significantly impact the living conditions of weavers have been identified, including disorganized operations, diversification of products, loan requirements, availability of raw materials, low returns, and marketing challenges. The weavers' level of satisfaction has decreased because of a range of concerns. Ultimately, the degree of satisfaction felt by handloom weavers is influenced by a multifaceted interplay of economic, cultural, and individual factors. [1].

To ascertain the factors impacting the handloom weaving practices of women weavers in the Lakhimpur District of Assam, another research study was conducted. It was also found that the income of weavers affects their level of participation. The performance and output of handloom goods were impacted by the rise in health-related issues among weavers. Weavers described excruciating levels of physical discomfort. Therefore, enhancing the working conditions and the compatibility of the weaver with the loom would aid in reducing the pain and suffering experienced by weavers. This would increase the income, performance, and output of the weavers [2].

With over 65% of all looms in the nation, the Northeastern states of India are home to the greatest concentration of handlooms. The study investigates the role of motivation in the entrepreneurship process within the cluster by analyzing entrepreneurial motivations, including ambitions, reasons for entering the industry, factors that facilitate entry into entrepreneurship, and the desire for their children to become entrepreneurs in the same industry. The cluster has undoubtedly developed into a hub for entrepreneurship with the primary objectives of generating income, being independent, and making a life [3].

The research study conducted by Ramswamy and Hmangaihzual intends to examine the strategies employed for promoting and distributing micro handloom firms throughout the rural region of North East India. The data used in this study is derived from primary sources, specifically from a structured questionnaire administered to 175 out of 325 entrepreneurs operating within the Thenzawl cluster. According to the survey, weavers encounter many challenges when trying to market their goods. It has also been discovered that the cluster is not experiencing the implementation of the federal government's ambitions to sell handloom items. To support tribal communities in this isolated region of northeastern India in realizing their Made in India goals, increased efforts in product distribution and promotion are needed [4].

An investigation is carried out to look at the sociological and demographic aspects that affect the handloom weavers' decision to become members of an Odisha cooperative society. The main determinants of handloom weavers' willingness to work under a WCS (Weavers' Cooperative Society) are their skill level and marital status, according to the results of the binary logistic regression study. With proper training, government policies should work to strengthen cooperative societies. [5].

The Manipuri handloom industry, which is Bangladesh's main ethnic handcrafted garment sector, has a troubled past, a hazy present, and an uncertain future. A research study is conducted to discuss the issues and future potential of this sector. This piece uses geographic information systems to pinpoint the locations of handloom product outlets based on visitor traffic, commercial prospects, and the accessibility of unprocessed materials. The outcome demonstrates the main causes for the fall in handloom weaving endeavors are the competitive market, capital scarcity, and low-profit margin [6].

A study is being carried out to investigate the factors that affect workers' occupational choices in the Assamese handloom sector and to concentrate on the factors that influence workers' occupational choices. The tested empirical model's findings indicate that family size, access to modern technology, annual income, and education are the primary elements that influence the transition from being reelers to being owners. Similarly, the crucial factors that facilitate the transformation of reelers into weavers include annual earnings, level of education, and availability of formal financial resources. The widespread availability of modern technology primarily drives the transition from weavers to handloom proprietors [7].

Kumar and Sulaiman investigated to identify the primary issues and obstacles related to the production and marketing of handloom manufacturing facilities in South India. The examination of the issues faced by the handloom units aids in determining the particular requirements of this industry and helps to focus policy and research efforts. The study's primary data were acquired from the sample handloom manufacturing facilities in South India. The investigation found that while handloom goods are becoming more and more popular both domestically and internationally, the handloom units are dealing with several issues related to manufacturing and marketing [8].

This study examines the difficulties faced by Himachal Pradesh's handloom weavers by providing a thorough overview of the handloom industry's value chain and the role that cooperative societies and tourism play in sustaining the demand for handloom products, particularly in areas that see a high volume of both domestic and foreign travel. The findings show that a more organized and enlarged handloom weavers market is necessary for the handloom sector to remain sustainable. The handloom industry is significant to the state economy [9].

A study has revealed that occupational health issues are present in all handloom weavers. Weavers' output has decreased significantly as a result of occupational health issues. The handloom weavers were in extremely vulnerable and impoverished socially, medically, and economically [10].

To improve the socioeconomic profile of weavers, a study was conducted to examine the socioeconomic conditions and issues facing the handloom weaving industry in East Godavari District. The research also sought to augment measures already in place for the industry's growth as well as those of APCO, handloom weaver cooperative societies, and weavers themselves [11].

3. Data and Methodology

The present study uses secondary data published by the Government of India. Most of the information we used for the analysis was about "The National Handloom Census of Weavers and Allied Workers" conducted by the "National Council of Applied Economic Research, New Delhi". As we use data from multiple census reports, we use a panel data framework for the analysis. We use both panel data regressions for modeling the dynamics.

3.1 Panel Data Regression Model

Following standard notions, we briefly describe the panel data models here. Below, we represent the common linear panel models.

$$y_{it} = \alpha_{it} + \beta_{it}^T x_{it} + u_{it} \quad (1)$$

Where the indices "i" and "t" represent the districts and year, and residual u_{it} is the random error term.

We make certain assumptions regarding the parameters, errors, and homogeneity of the regressors. These assumptions allow us to construct a range of possible models for analyzing panel data. The parameter's homogeneity is one of the common assumptions. We assume that the error term consists of two distinct components, one of which is unique to each individual and remains constant throughout time.

Here is the estimated fixed effect model for the variables considered in this study.

$$(\text{Production})_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{HHs})_{it} + \beta_2(\text{HHsize})_{it} + \beta_3(\text{Debt})_{it} + \beta_4(\text{WorkingDays})_{it} + \beta_5(\text{Membership})_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

4. Results and Discussion

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variables	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Production	58	11	1371097	85352.81	232351.94
HHs	58	568	1269506	101727.03	241114.12
HH size	58	2.58	6.04	4.4359	0.87
Debt	58	0	27964	1621.93	4570.46
Working Days	58	82	295	215.71	58.50
Membership	58	1	253076	16270.10	36972.45
Valid N (list wise)	58				

Table 2: Correlation Matrix

Variables	Production	HHs	HH size	Debt	Working Days	Membership
Production	1.0000	0.9763**	-0.0862	0.1014	-0.1984	0.7820**
HHs		1.0000	-0.1062	0.2124	0.1759	0.7554**
HH size			1.0000	-0.2973*	-0.2941*	-0.3049*
Debt				1.0000	0.1948	0.2876*
Working Days					1.0000	0.0344
Membership						1.0000

** , * indicates that the estimated coefficient is significant at 1 and 5 percent level

Table 3: Fixed Effects Model Estimation Results

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-ratio	p-value
Constant	19546.0	52322.3	0.3736	0.7120
Number of Households	0.771986	0.220811	3.496	0.0019***
Household size	-4627.16	5799.10	-0.7979	0.4327
Debt	-1.81853	1.26926	-1.433	0.1648
Working Days	-32.8739	202.270	-0.1625	0.8723
Membership	1.09656	0.176229	6.222	<0.0001***

LSDV R-squared: 0.994793

Within R-squared: 0.789028

LSDV F (33, 24) (p=8.50e-21)

Durbin-Watson: 1.914724

Test for differing group intercepts = P (F (28, 24) > 3.44644) = 0.00148264

Breusch-Pagan test - test statistic: = 4.06 (p-value = 0.043)

Hausman test - test statistic= 15.23 (p-value = 0.009)

Table 1 contains descriptive statistics, Table 2 provides the correlation coefficients of all of the variables used in the regression analysis. We have selected five independent variables for the panel regression, which include the number of handloom households (HHs), household size (HH size), total debt of the handloom households (Debt), average number of working days (Working Days), and membership in a cooperative society, SHG, or production company (Membership), about the dependent variable Total Household Handloom Production (Production). The tests for different group intercepts ($P < 0.05$), the Breusch-Pagan test ($P < 0.05$), and the Hausman test ($P < 0.05$) show that the fixed effect model is better than the pooled OLS and random effect models. States are defined as cross-section units. $i = 1, 2, \dots, 29$.

The parameter estimates in Table 3 indicate the variable HHs are statistically significant ($t = 3.496$, $p < .001$). As HHs increase by one unit, production increases by 0.772 units by holding all other variables constant. The variable membership is statistically significant ($t = 6.222$, $p < .001$). As membership increases by one unit, production increases by 1.097 units. The variable HHsize is not statistically significant ($t = -0.798$, $p > 0.05$). Similarly, the variables debt ($t = -1.433$, $p > 0.05$) and number of working days ($t = -0.163$, $p > 0.05$) are insignificant for having an impact on production. Essentially, this estimate shows that India's handloom production will increase with the increase in the number of handloom households and their membership in cooperative societies, SHGs, and

production companies. The presented empirical evidence indicates that variables like the number of handloom households and membership in cooperative societies, SHGs, and production companies influence handloom production. Specifically, the estimated model, which includes five independent variables, accounted for 79 percent of the variance in total household handloom production in India.

The results demonstrate the significant role that membership in cooperatives, SHGs, and companies plays in contributing to overall production. It also indicates that these associations can reduce household uncertainties in their production engagement. This could be because these organizations facilitate the easy acquisition of raw materials and other necessary supplies for their members, and they may also offer buy-back programs. This significant contribution suggests active policy interventions to bring unorganized houses under the umbrella of these organizations, thereby fostering further growth in the sector.

5. Conclusion

The handloom industry contributes significantly to the Indian economy in several ways, such as creating jobs, empowering women, and fostering strong ties with the agricultural sector. The current study looks into the important variables that affect the output generation performance of the handloom industry. The results from the analysis show that the number of households engaged in weaving and their membership in cooperative societies have a significant effect on the total output from the handloom sector. It explains how collectives can contribute to output generation and suggests considering government interventions to bring the unorganized units under the umbrella of cooperatives and similar organizations for better sector performance.

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